

**Spiritual renewal in new Uzbekistan: interdependence, concept, content -
essence of building a civil society**

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Abstract: In this article, the processes of national and spiritual revival in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence and the role of spiritual renewal in the construction of civil society are scientifically analyzed.

Keywords: "Spirituality", "high spirituality", civil society, sense of belonging, spiritual renewal and growth, criteria forming spirituality, globalization, spiritual threats, human factor in the development of civil society, foundations of civil society, national spiritual heritage and values, democratic universal principles.

Introduction

Building civil society is inextricably linked with its spiritual foundations. The thinking, way of life, and spiritual views of any people or nation are not formed by themselves, in a vacuum. Their emergence and development are based on specific historical, natural and social factors. Due to independence, special attention was paid to the spiritual foundations of our society. The former Soviet state's policy of looking down on spirituality has ended. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's work "New Uzbekistan Strategy" is important in understanding the

interdependence of spirituality and civil society. "We all understand well that if the body of society is economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. We rely on these two strong foundations in building a new Uzbekistan, that is, a strong economy based on market principles and a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors, national and universal values ¹.

There are many definitions of the concept of "spirituality" that are expressed in scientific, philosophical, literary or ordinary language. Every enlightened person has his own philosophical approach, political views and e' It is natural to give different definitions and descriptions if it originates from his belief and thinking. That is why it is appropriate not to be surprised when you come across different opinions on this issue in scientific literature and daily press, but to accept them as an expression of the unique worldview and observation style of each author. First President I. Karimov in his work entitled "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" defines spirituality as follows: "Spirituality is something that calls a person to spiritual purification, spiritual growth, strengthens a person's inner world, will, and faith. the incomparable force that heals and awakens his conscience is the criterion of all his views ². The feeling of belonging is a set of conditions and factors that call for citizens' birthplace, Motherland, independence, preservation, protection, and further development.

I, an Uzbek, every person I consider a citizen of Uzbekistan should live, aspire, and be active with this feeling.

A sense of belonging:

¹Sh. M. Mirziyoyev . New Uzbekistandevlopmentstrategy . - T.: Uzbekistan , 2021.- 267 - p.

²IA Karimov. A high moral **character** is an indomitable force. - T.: "Ma ' Naviyat", 2008, - 19 pages.

- 1) Affection of a person in relation to the people around him;
- 2) Affection to the family;
- 3) the area ;
- 4) Nationality;
- 5) These are cases related to the feeling of belonging to the country, the Motherland.

The rise of the spiritual world of a person and the sense of courage are inextricably linked with the implementation of the tasks of building a civil society. Citizens' participation in state and community management is clearly manifested in strengthening their inner world and will, strengthening their faith. "It should be taken into account that a person's attitude to the life of society, respecting the laws, following the principles of justice, valuing people, considering their rights and freedoms as the highest value, living honestly and cleanly is a practical expression of their high spiritual world and sense of belonging. Civil society construction in this sense, it can be seen that it is inextricably linked with the qualities of a person's high spirituality and sense of belonging ³. " Civil society is a social space. It is clearly manifested in the relations of citizens with the state and society. Civil society is a society in which active participation of citizens in the management of the state and society is ensured through relevant civil society institutions. It is regulated and implemented by relevant laws. Civil society in this sense is an important condition for building a democratic society. The higher the morale and sense of belonging of

³AO Tamurodov . The study of "Civil Society" is a methodological complex. Tashkent, 2017. - 115 - p.

the society, the more the opportunities for the implementation of civil society development tasks will increase. It is permissible to quote the following points from President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's "New Uzbekistan Strategy" . "We are creating wide opportunities for young people, we are entrusting them with important positions. They have knowledge and talent, but it is felt that some of them have moved away from our national soil and national spirituality. They want to quickly and urgently implement the experience in foreign countries where they have studied. However, they do not think about ⁴how many hundreds of years these countries have achieved such a result ." The concept of "high spirituality" is a unique criterion that determines the level of spiritual development of society. It shows the unique qualities of the life of the society as a criterion of the spiritual world, inner world, beliefs and views of every person in the society. High spirituality is inextricably linked with the society's national spiritual heritage and values, as well as the development of science, the experience and achievements of building a democratic society.

The construction of civil society is related to the understanding of spirituality and the sense of belonging, the criteria that form it. The construction of the civil society relies on the specific national characteristics related to the national-spiritual heritage and values of each nation and takes into account the achievements of the peoples of the world. Spirituality is absorbed into the blood and bones of a person over the years with mother's milk, family upbringing, ancestors' education, feeling of the Motherland, and the sometimes bitter and sometimes joyful lessons of this life. In particular, closeness to nature and people, always thinking about the good in life,

⁴Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. Development strategy of new Uzbekistan . - T.: Uzbekistan , 2021. - 271 - p.

honest work, and enjoying the world's incomparable blessings and beauties feed spirituality and strengthen it even more.

To sum up, the experience of the peoples of the world, the complex development paths they have taken, the lessons and conclusions in this regard indicate that wherever the state and society progress, it is a sufficient condition for the people to live peacefully, to live with noble and great goals. - if the conditions are created, then there will be an environment of free thinking and, on this basis, new opportunities for realizing spiritual growth and a sense of belonging.

Reference :

1. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyotstrategiyasi. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2021.- 267 – bet.
2. I.A. Karimov. Yuksak ma’naviyat – engilmas kuch. – T.: “Ma’naviyat”, 2008, - 19 bet.
3. A.O‘tamurodov. “Fuqarolik jamiyati” fanidan o‘quv – uslubiy majmua. Toshkent, 2017.- 115 – bet.
4. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2021.- 271 – bet.

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